

PRAGMATIC APPROACH ON TRANSLATING TOURISTIC TEXTS

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Știm cu toții că astăzi sectorul turismului este unul dintre pilonii economiei și că numărul vizitatorilor străini este în creștere. Dezvoltarea turismului a influențat în mare măsură necesitatea de a reda în diferite limbi informațiile oferite pe site-urile turistice locale, pe paginile web de promovare regională sau pe site-urile organizațiilor turistice comerciale internaționale (de exemplu, companii aeriene, companii de croazieră, tur-operatori etc.). În consecință, creșterea turismului internațional și cel local din ultimii ani, împreună cu globalizarea pieței, au determinat creșterea cererii de traduceri legate de turism. Așadar, traducerea în domeniul turismului poate fi o provocare, deoarece există atât de multe limbi cu propriile standarde și realități (cultureme). Respectiv, această lucrare încearcă să analizeze dificultățile de traducere ale textelor turistice ca mijloc de îmbunătățire a traducerii textelor și a site-urilor web din domeniul turismului pentru a face o distincție între „a traduce o cultură” și „traducere culturală”

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Considering the fact that tourism has become one of the central phenomena of a postmodern society greatly owing to its liaison with language. Especially prominent is the link between tourism and English language which, being the global lingua franca, not only monopolies all negotiations/transactions that take place in a tourist destination, but also functions as a creator of a destination's many realities, indeed as the very embodiment of processes in tourism.

Tourism is an activity which involves the direct contact between cultures and all that this concept includes namely folklore, customs,

gastronomy, dancing, rules, etc. This makes us consider the language of tourism an element of inestimable value between tourists and the place they are visiting and, above all, a joint element between the local and foreign cultures involved.

Consequently, this situation requires high quality tourist texts, especially translations, so as to guarantee effective and clear communication between local people and culture and real or potential tourists.

Tourist texts present several difficulties that are based on the features that we have seen before. Nevertheless, the major problem in translating tourist discourse is due to its cultural content.

This type of text describes and informs about other cultures and therefore, their main difficulty is to introduce a reality (being a city, a country, a type of food, etc.) to a person who may have never heard of it [1, p. 20].

Tourism discourse has a socio-institutional character. Various organisations linked with this industry may be assigned to the institutes of tourism discourse: tour operators; travel firms and agencies; air and railway ticket offices; PR and advertising agencies. The destination of the expansive tourist universe may be national tourism organisations, the Travel Agency of the Republic of Moldova, travel agencies and companies, tour operators, guides, hotel workers, restaurants, museums, animators and many others. They come with a lot of offers, services, and ideas to the audience. Both the target audience and the viewpoint can represent the receiver. Tourist discourse is a special mass information and status-oriented institutional discourse. In pragmatic orientation, referring to selling tourist products and high information richness, tourist discourse is closer to advertising discourse. [7, p.150-152]

The terminology which approaches tourism is nowadays very diverse and very extensive, being created both by the fields implied in tourism, as well as by those who work with it in its administration.

Thus, as the tourism industry implies in more independent spheres, the same way its terminology has a high degree of implication of notions from all the participative fields. We can broadly mention:

1. Services of tourism organisation, which elaborate, promote and sell touristic products: *organised voyage, tourism zonation, days of functioning, transfer, transfer driver, recommendation, contractual liability, reconfirming, tourist information office, circuit travel, etc.;*

2. Services of accommodation (*hotels, motels, pensions, rest houses* etc.): *hotelier, reception, receptionist, room, single room, the best available, contingent of places, family room, bed, double bed, bunk, towel, sheet, bed linen, vacuum cleaner, porter, lifter, home stage, full board, the arrival registration, etc.*; [2, p.66].

3. Public food (*restaurants, cafes, bars, etc.*) *maître d'hôtel, waiter, menu, consumption, couvert, disposal, entrée, appetiser, breakfast, supper, bain-marie, plateau, bowl, cup, glass, pliers, baking, fryer, meat grinder, slicing machine, frapper, cocotiera, seafood, glass, cold meal, hot meal, order note, bill, etc.*;

4. The public transportation (the *auto, air, railway, sea, river* one etc.): *the race number, road sheet, bus, auto-service, highway, traffic code, personal train, ticket platform, sleeping carriage, wagon bar, four-foot way, airline company, charter plane, time limit charter, compartment, economic class, tourist class, marine coast, wharf, landing, cruise ship, starboard, free shipping permit, driver's licence, transit, city tour, etc.*;

5. The production field (*souvenirs, hotel furniture, travel equipment*): *jewellery, postcards, brochure, tourist leaflet, travel equipment, front-desk, backpack, tent, suitcase, boots, skis*;

6. The commerce field: *sales volume, duty-free shop, improvement, sample, price, direct selling, cash selling, etc.*

7. Economy: *leasing, open leasing, commercial balance, payment balance, bank, banknote, cheque, market research, demand, offer, cession, commission, tax, hotel contract, etc.*;

8. Rest and recreation fields (*thematic parks, interest clubs, games rooms, etc.*): *amusement park, water park, nightclub, air club, riding club, disco-video club, mountain resort, thermal resort, touristic resort, etc.*;

9. Sports (*alpinism, cycling, swimming, horse riding, etc.*): *climbing, climbing team, summer climb, winter climb, artificial structures climb, beginners path, advanced path, cable car, pool, swimming pool, kayak, riding trip, etc.* [35, p.76].

Given the fact that the tourism industry is developing at a speedy pace and new types of tourism are emerging, studying the creation of tourism advertising and its impact on the consumer will always be relevant. Linguistics has only recently recognised the field of tourism as an important context to study. Researchers such as N.N Michailov.,

Jaworski Adam and Pritchard Keely combine the fields of sociolinguistics and tourism. Thus, linguistic analysis in tourism advertising requires further research.

In tourist texts/ advertisements, the lexical and semantic approach has a very important status. For instance, in every tourism related literature there are neologisms, invented words, Realia, idioms, archaic words, polysemy, and wordplay and so on. All of these create a brand-new world full of special effects on the reader, in order to persuade them to operate with goods provided by those who sell them via tourist texts/ advertisements.

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, **neologism** refers to a new word or expression, or a new meaning for an existing word. Neologisms are usually used in tourist texts/ advertisements to define invented or real things. For example, *responsible tourism* is often used in mostly discussing the topic of the financial crises. There were many expressions derived from the word “vacation”. Speakers defined their vacation as their *mancation* (taking vacation only in group of other men), *greycation* (taking vacation together with older generations of your family), *haycation* (taking vacation on a farm), *playcation* (vacation where your only intention is to play or have fun without considering any history, heritage, etc.), *daycation* (a vacation for one day), *fake-ation* (where most of you vacation time is spent working), *staycation* (staying + vacation: staying at home for vacation, mostly used in times of financial crises when people cannot afford longer vacations away from home). A term to *sofalize* was also used for staying at home and communicating only electronically.

According to Merriam Webster dictionary, an **idiom** represents an expression in the usage of a language that is peculiar to itself either in having a meaning that cannot be derived from the conjoined meanings of its elements or in its grammatically atypical use of words. Nowadays, and thanks to low-cost airlines, it's very common for people to travel a few times throughout the year to many different places all around the world. For this reason, we might have heard new idioms in English that we didn't quite understand and we'd like to learn; or perhaps we're just looking for new vocabulary to use on our next trip and leave the people we're going with amazed with our new-found knowledge. Below, we're going to take a look at a few common English idioms for travelling or related to tourism:

- *To travel/ pack light*- when someone says they need to pack or travel light, it means they can't bring a lot of things with them on their trip.

- *Break the journey* means they decide to stop somewhere for a while during a long journey [11]

Polysemy represents the phenomena where a word has two or more meanings, usually resulting from the modification and development of the original meaning of this word. Polysemic is the English term “*host*.” This word originally had the meaning “*a person who has invested guests*” [3, p. 152], then it was terminology with the meaning “*the landlord of a hotel or inn, also sometimes of a restaurant*” [3, p. 152]. Later, with the development of the tourism sector, this meaning was clarified, as a result of which in English the term “*host*” has the following meanings: *a representative of the group (organiser) that may array optional excursions and answer questions but does not have escort authority* [6, p. 201 - 222]: Your local host can suggest optional tours or ideas for independent exploring and dining;

Partial synonyms, on the other hand, occur when words have very closely related meanings. The meanings are not exactly the same, only partially, but close enough to relay the same message. Partial synonyms can differ in their collocation, register, and regional/social variation, for example, *The tickets can only be bought online.* vs *The tickets can only be purchased online.* Generally, buy and purchase mean ‘to obtain something by paying money for it’. However, the two words differ in their register. Buy is considered a general term, whereas purchase is often used in a more formal context.

A **collocation** is two or more words that often go together. There are several different types of collocation related to tourism that are made from combinations of verb, noun, adjective etc. Some of the most common are:

- **adjective + noun:** *I attended a meeting to promote **rural tourism**.* (to a particular place: rural, space)/ *We look forward to your visit to this 'little golden part of Devon' where green tourism is encouraged.* (not harming the environment: eco, green) [5]

- **verb + noun:** *The Olympic games will create jobs and **boost tourism**.* (increase tourism: boost, enhance, improve, increase)/ *The railway also brought the first mass tourism to the Yorkshire Dales in*

the 19th century. (encourage tourism: attract, bring, develop, encourage, promote, revive, stimulate, support) [5]

- **noun + noun:** *Recent **tourism marketing** campaigns have been a huge success.* (development: development, marketing, promotion)/ *Prague was enjoying a tourism boom.* (increase: boom) [5]

- **verb + preposition:** *The town **survives** mainly **through** tourism.* [13]

- **phrase:** *My family and I visited Singapore for 3 days and I have to say this trip was definitely the **holiday of a lifetime**.* [10]

Stylistic devices, also known as figures of speech or rhetorical devices, have an important impact on the reader because they affect the meaning of the message received by them.

Alliteration is the intentional iteration of an initial sound in two or more words. For example, take the expression often used in the mass tourism industry “*Sun, Sea and Sand Holiday*”. The repeated consonant [s] in this case makes the message more memorable.

A **metaphor** is a figure of speech in which a person moves from one sense of a word to another by making an implicit analogy. For example, “*Enjoy the beauty and grandeur of this land of legend and dreams.*”, expressing the idea that “It is a land famous for its legends and is like a dream”.

Pun is a literary device that is also known as a “play on words”. Puns can be seen as words that sound the same but have different etymologies. For example, the word “connections” will have different meanings in different contexts. “*To be a successful frequent flyer you need a lot of connections*” (Pun of the Day), where “connections” can mean both “*number of connections in a flight*” and “*connections with people*”, but in this context the former is correct [9].

The pragmatic approach refers to the techniques that the translator uses to translate any kind of text. There are a lot of techniques that are useful and really necessary when translating texts especially in the field of tourism. In the tourism text translating process, the translators intend to convey a certain cultural message, which is actively helping the readers to recognize the translated texts. The two types of translation techniques are: the direct translation technique and the indirect translation technique. The direct translation technique includes borrowing, loan word or calque and literal translation. The indirect translation technique has transposition, modulation, reformulation or equivalence, adaptation, compensation,

expansion, reduction, description, generalization, omission, addition, substitution [12, p. 80].

Cultural Borrowing is the first alternative is to transfer a ST expression verbatim into the TT. This process is termed cultural borrowing. With that being said, **borrowings** are one of the main sources of enriching a language. This is the case in the following example:

Tradițional, ornamental (rombul) era brodat pe ia de nuntă și pe prosoapele din Casa Mare.

Traditionally, the ornament was embroidered on the wedding IA (the IA is a traditional embroidered blouse on white cotton, flax or silk) and on the towels in Casa Mare (the traditional guest house).

In this example, the Realia name of *ia* and *Casa Mare*, referring to traditional Moldovan motifs and places, was preserved, moreover for the common reader not knowing the cultural specific identity of Moldova a clarifying specification was added e.g. for *IA- a traditional embroidered blouse on white cotton, flax or silk* and *the traditional guest house* for *Casa Mare- the traditional guest house*.

Calque refers to the rendering of each element of the source-text word or phrase into the target language literally.

Vatra medievală cu biserica „Nașterea Maicii Domnului” din 1882.
The medieval village area with the church ”Birth of the Virgin Mary” from 1882.

The calque translation of the „Nașterea Maicii Domnului” is justified by the fact that Orthodox Churches uses this term in order to describe the birth of the Blessed Virgin Mary on its traditional fixed date of September 8, nine months after the December 8 celebration of her Immaculate Conception as the child of Saints Joachim and Anne. Moreover, other sources would use for translation of the term as The Nativity of the Blessed Virgin Mary in order to preserve the colourful concept of the birth word.

Cultural Adaptation refers to the replacing of the unfamiliar with familiar.

Pentru iubitorii de carne, o mâncare moldovenească grozavă de care vă veți bucura este frigăruiul. Acest frigărui moldovenesc îmbină carne fragedă la grătar și legume.

*For meat lovers, a great Moldovan food you'll enjoy is the **grilled kebab**. This **Moldovan kebab skewers** tender grilled meat and vegetables together.*

In the above example, we see that the food item name *frigăru* was given equivalence in English *kebab*. Nonetheless, it should be pointed out that knowledge of translator's background in the Moldovan culture, and the experience in this domain is a must quality, because the lack of any of these could produce some misunderstandings, due to the fact that kebab in other countries it is a sliced meat served on a plate with various accompaniments, stuffed into a pita or other type of bread as a sandwich, or wrapped in a thin flatbread such as lavash.

To take into account **transposition**, then it involves a shift from one grammatical category to another, while still preserving the meaning. This translation technique is often necessary between languages with different grammatical structures. Here is an example of that:

Life in the Rhythm of the Heartbeat!

Viața bate în ritmul inimii!

This example can be schematically analysed as it follows: N+Prep+Art+N+Prep+Art+N, which is a feature of the English language and transposing it into Romanian we will have another part of speech structure: N+V+Pre+Art+N phrase. From this we can deduce that while rendering the advertising language from a SL into a TL, it is important to analyse the structure of this sublanguage to adequately meet the needs of the TL sublanguage requirements.

One of the most common translation technique used is *equivalence*. The equivalent translation of a term is the most optimal method of translation. However, this method can only be used if the level of social development of the source and target language countries coincides. There is an example:

Ziua va începe cu o drumeție pronind din Chișinău spre Cricova potrivit traseului: Chișinău-Bunet-Făurești-Cricova.

The day will begin with a hike from Chisinau to Cricova following the itinerary: Chisinau-Bunet-Fauresti-Cricova.

The translator used equivalent terms like in *traseu* and *itinerary*, due to practically identical meaning of the selected pairs of terms; *traseu* – road that a vehicle or a person travels on (permanently), while *itinerary* is an established or selected course of travel.

The concept of **explicitation** was introduced by Vinay and Darbelnet, who defined it as a stylistic translation technique which consists of making explicit in the target language what remains implicit in the source

language because it is apparent from either the context or the situation [8, p.331].

*Moldovenii cântă adesea la **cobza**, un instrument musical tipic pentru muzica tradițională românească.*

*Moldovans often play the **cobza**, a wooden stringed instrument similar to the lute that is common in traditional Romanian music.*

Here we can observe the fact that the translator added a piece of information to the TT, in order to be more specific about this musical instrument and at the same time to make the audience better to understand the text.

Conclusions

Over and done with this article we wanted to subsidise to the creation of a contrastive study of the terminology in the field of tourism from Romanian to English. In accordance to this, we would like to draw some conclusions:

1. When we discuss the translation of tourist texts from Romanian to English or vice versa, it is very important to make a distinction between the two terms 'translating culture' and 'cultural translation'. Translating culture, in a narrow sense, refers to the act of transferring meaning from one specific culture-bearing language to another. Cultural translation refers to a dynamic process where everyone and everything that are a part of the interaction in translation undergo change, where notions are constructed about other cultures and about oneself. That is to say, translating culture is an act only in translation and cultural translation is the understanding and rendering of cultural concepts. Translating tourist texts is not simply translating culture, but also involves cultural translation. In a sense, translating tourist texts means translating the source culture to the reader.

2. Translation of tourist texts is a kind of publicity activity. Its essence is that the translator should attempt to produce the same effect on the target language readers as is produced by the original on the source language readers. Moldovan or British readers seldom have difficulty in understanding the original because they share the same cultural background with the writer. However, cultural discrepancies will hinder foreign readers from understanding such texts properly. Therefore translators should adopt an appropriate method to adjust the version to help readers comprehend the texts. Otherwise, they will

find the translation requiring so much effort to understand that they are likely to stop reading, unless they are very highly motivated.

3. It seems necessary for an acceptable translation to produce the same (or at least similar) effects on the TT readers as those created by the original work on its readers. This paper may show that a translator does not appear to be successful in their challenging task of efficiently rendering the culture-specific items when they sacrifice, or at least minimizes, the effect of realia in favour of preserving graphical or lexical forms of source language. In other words, a competent translator is advised not to deprive the TL reader of enjoying, or even recognizing, the realia either in the name of fidelity or brevity.

Referințe bibliografice

1. BAKER, M.(ed.) – Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies, London, Routledge,2004 p.575
2. BRUNETTE, Terminology For Translation Quality Assessment: A Comparison of TQA Practices, in the Translator, Vol.6, Nr.9, 2000, p.p 298
3. Dictionary of Leisure, Travel and Tourism. Third edition. London: A&C Black Publishers Ltd, 2006. – 378
4. LEPPihalme, R., “Culture bumps: an empirical approach to the translation of allusions”, Helsinki: Multilingual Matters, 1997, 241p.
5. Macmillan Dictionary
6. SIMMONS J. Railways, Hotels, and Tourism in Great Britain (1839-1914) // Journal of Contemporary History. 1984. Vol. 19., 960p.
7. Tourism Discourse And Its Terminology,Vakhidova Fotima Saidovna, Novateur Publications,Journalnx- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, Volume 7, ISSUE 3, Mar. -2021, p.485
8. VINAY, D.P., J. Darbelnet. 1958, “Stylistique comparée du français et de l’anglais. Méthode de traduction”, Paris, Didier, 1958, 342 p.
9. <https://hostelgeeks.com/travel-puns-jokes-captions-tiktok-instagram/> [Accesat 29.03.22]

10. <https://ieltspractiseonline.com/collocations-idioms-topic-travelling/> [Accesat 29.03.22]
11. <https://nikateacher.com/common-english-idioms-for-travelling/> [Accesat 29.03.22]
12. https://repository.uksw.edu/bitstream/123456789/3211/2/ART_Nesya%20N-Andrew%20T_Translation%20techniques_Full%20text.pdf, p. 80]. [Accesat 15.04.22]
13. <https://www.freecollocation.com/search?word=tourism> [Accesat 29.03.22]